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A Complete Construal of Consciousness – Comprehensible?

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Abstract

Consciousness – has been a strong pre-occupation of the thinking minds down the centuries. It is the fundamental requirement for any meaningful communication. This paper in its first section tries to have some basic insights into the concept of consciousness and its features such as, unity, intentionality, selectivity and transience. The second section, therefore, challenges this notion of reductionism from different angles, like, in the contexts of mind-body relationships, the construal of physical laws and the realistic picture of science. As the notion of consciousness seems to be prominent in the fields of quantum physics, the third and last section explores the notion of consciousness to analyze whether consciousness creates reality and to see whether there are so-called ‘conscious activities’ at the atomic/cellular domains. Finally, the paper concludes, basing on the generally-accepted principle, that the ‘whole’ is always more than its ‘constituents’, that it is high impossible to have complete comprehension of consciousness.

Introduction

Consciousness is a basic experience of my own feelings and states of mind. Though it is an existential experience, there are fundamental questions about consciousness that baffle us: Is there any sure way to know what others think, or even to know whether they can think? So, what is consciousness? Where does it come

from? Why did evolution put it there in the first place? Are these conscious experiences there only for our safety? How does it differ from the consciousness of animals, if they had one? When do the children begin to have or recognize their conscious experiences? – are some of the basic questions that have kept human beings busy for centuries.

Further, on the one hand we claim that only human beings are gifted with consciousness, with which they can reflect and decide to act, but on the other, over centuries, we come across the painful and heinous activities of hatred and disharmony, among the individuals, societies and nations; the horrible experiences of the Nazi dictatorship, the current socio-economic turmoil all over the globe, cold wars among the powerful nations, the fear of atomic annihilation, the dangers of planetary environmental disasters, and the chaotic developments, the current situations of Covid-19; the enormous damages that are done to the environment and nature around us due to our selfish and shortsighted activities of humanity – all these push people to the edge of their peaceful and happy lives. We are once again forced to see what do we exactly mean by consciousness and conscious actions and their consequences.

To address those perennial questions mere scientific and physical approaches are not enough. For instance, how are brain-consciousness (or body-mind/self/soul) are related? How the microscopic neurons, about 100 billion, which are physical can produce non-physical (spiritual/mental) experiences? How are the unconscious neurons create (or contain) consciousness? How are we to get conscious experience of the external world outside of us? and a more troublesome question would be, how are we conscious of our consciousness? Does the brain contribute anything in turning the meaningless world into a meaningful one? All these deep questions cannot be meaningfully dealt with by any one discipline; they require interdisciplinary approach.

Human beings are no more seen in the dichotomies of ‘rational’ and ‘spiritual’, ‘material’ and non-material. The

Cartesian dualism has affected the Western thoughts since the time of Descartes. But the twentieth century has seen a shift in that understanding, to see a person in totality, as a ‘psychosomatic being’, where the ‘bodily’ and the ‘spiritual’ aspects are given equal importance. There is no superiority, or inferiority between them. So currently accepted view is that “either that a human being is an animated body or that [s]/he is an embodied soul” (John Macquarrie 1982:53).

It is in this context that the paper attempts to deal with the concept of consciousness to see whether one can comprehend it totally. In the first section, the paper, tries to have some basic insights into the concept of consciousness and its features such as, unity, intentionality, selectivity and transience. Generally, the tendency to reduce the whole to its components motivates one to see consciousness purely in terms of brain (physical) functions. The second section, therefore, challenges the notion of reductionism from different angles, like, in the contexts of mind-body relationships, the construal of physical laws and the realistic picture of science. As the notion of consciousness seems to be prominent in the fields of quantum physics, the third and last section explores the notion of consciousness to analyze whether consciousness creates reality and to see whether there are so-called ‘conscious activities’ at the atomic/cellular domains. Finally, the paper concludes, based on the generally accepted principle that the ‘whole’ is very often more than its ‘constituents,’ that it is nigh impossible to have complete comprehension of consciousness; this fact, however, need not deter human beings from exploring further into the existential and essential fact of consciousness, which can help us in identifying the purpose and meaning of our lives.

I Consciousness and Its Characteristics

1. Consciousness – Down the Centuries

It is very difficult to define what consciousness is, though we all know what it means to be conscious, or unconscious or semi-

conscious, from our own experiences and those of the others. We are conscious not only of ourselves, but also of others to learn about them, to communicate, to understand their motivations, including their reward and punishment systems.

Consciousness is often understood as pure essence of awareness, processing every bit of information very rapidly – seeing, analyzing, understanding, identifying and concluding – all taking place very fast, seamlessly and effortlessly. The conscious mind tells me who I am, who the other person is and what a thing in front of me is. It is the most fundamental phenomenon of our existence; without this we cannot prove that we or anything else exists. Sometimes I may not know where I am, why I am there in that place, what the time is, etc. but still I know, I exist, because I can experience it.

However, lots of things are done unconsciously. If a task is repeated, it is programmed in our brain so deeply that it can be done unconsciously. Unconscious mind can download lots of information, much faster than the conscious mind can deal with. Unconscious fears, some traumatic experiences in the childhood affect us even later; we need just conscious recognition of unconscious problems.

Such fundamental questions of conscious and existential experiences have been the focus of the ancient thinkers down the centuries. *Plato* (428-348 BC) spoke of three divisions of mind – the *rational*, the *appetitive* and the *temperamental*. But he did not develop on how they are related. He was more interested in the ‘World of Ideas’, than on the body and senses. *Aristotle* (384-322 BC) gave more importance to senses in acquiring knowledge, so much so, there is nothing in the intellect that was not first in the senses. However, he was convinced that, in human persons, there was *unity between body and body*. *Augustine* (354-430 AD) and many other Christian thinkers looked at the whole issue only as a mystery to marvel at, and not as a problem to be solved. *Thomas*

Aquinas (1225-1274 AD) also stressed upon the unity of body and mind, so *it is* “I” who eat, suffer, sleep, feel and not my ‘body.’

In the West, the whole issue took a different turn with Rene Descartes (1596-1650 AD), who brought in the ‘dualistic’ approach to the study of body/brain and mind/consciousness, by insisting upon two types of realities, totally different from each other, namely, the thinking thing (*res cogitans*) and extended thing (*res extensa*). But how they are related to each other, and how they both mutually influence in our ordinary lives, is beyond our complete comprehension. In clarifying this matter to Princess Elizabeth of Bohemia, he openly declared: “It does not seem to me that the human mind is capable of conceiving quite distinctly and at the same time both the distinction between mind and body, and their union” (cfr. William E. Seager 1988; Justin Skirry).

Nicholas Malebranche, a French Oratorian Catholic priest and rationalist philosopher (1638-1715 AD), evaded, rather dissolved, the issue by saying that God is the only real agent in making the body and mind interact, while humans are only apparent doers. Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Leibnitz, a German mathematician, philosopher, scientist and diplomat (1646-1716 AD), explained the unity between mind and body in terms of pre-established harmony. Spinoza (1632-77) held only God (or Nature) as the only reality and there are no agents outside this one major reality.

2. Characteristics of Consciousness

In the modern times, interdisciplinary disciplines are making conscious efforts to study consciousness. Before we reflect upon some insights from the fields Brain-studies and Quantum Physics, there is a general consensus regarding the basic characteristics of consciousness. The main features of consciousness are Unity, Selectivity (often resulting in blindness to other factors), Intentionality and Transience; for instance, if one is exploring a dark cave, with a narrow focused torch light – in order to get an

overall idea of the cave, one needs to combine all the examined spots together (unity); one focuses on something to know what it is (selectivity); one intends to know about it (intentionality) and one constantly shifts one's attention to different parts of the cave to know more (transience).

- a) *Unity or single state* – the brain coordinates all the sensory inputs from various sources and makes it as one integrated piece of information (the colour, texture and the taste of an apple!); it feels a single state (e.g. watching a movie – integrating sound, visuals, imagining the situation there in it etc).
- b) *Intentionality* – consciousness is always focused on something. The focus may be something on external or internal, real or imaginary, but it needs something to be focused.
- c) *Selectivity* – it focuses on something relevant and interesting; we cannot focus on everything at the same time. We filter out everything else, whatever is irrelevant, in order to pay attention to the chosen one. It is also known as *Cocktail party phenomena* – In a party when we talk to someone in front of us, all the other conversations become a background noise; we may hear them perfectly but we don't pay attention. (In laboratories, experiments are done on what is known as, *dichotic listening* – two different messages (or music) are played in two ears, with the different ear phones; the person is asked to listen to only one, and he/she cannot remember anything that was played on the other side! If the speaker is changed on the other side, the listener does not even notice it). Selectivity results in *Change (in-attentional) blindness* – when one looks at a picture, and if it is changed in a moment, one may not notice the changes in it, or even that the picture itself is changed, unless one has paid attention to something very outstanding or unusual there, because one's focus is very narrowed down. One can focus on only

one thing at a time, what one chooses to... and becomes blind to all other things. It is easy, therefore, to miss out something that one is not looking for.¹

- d) *Transience* – Our consciousness is always moving, shifting around. We always look around; if we are in a jungle, where the possibilities of some animals' attack, we cannot read a book there peacefully with total concentration; in general, when there is more anxiety, more shifting of the consciousness takes place.

3. Consciousness – Fundamental for Communication

We assume the consciousness of the others and without which we cannot communicate with them. Theory of mind (ToM), the term coined by Premack and Woodruff, is defined as the cognitive ability to understand and take into account another individual's mental state or of “mind-reading” (David Premack & Guy Woodruff 1978: 515-526). We have the capacity to understand other people by ascribing mental states to them; we know that others' mental states may be different from our own states and also know that beliefs, desires, intentions, emotions, and thoughts also differ. From the childhood we begin to learn that people don't share the same thoughts and feelings as we do develop; theory of mind implies a child's ability to “tune-in” to other people's viewpoints; this ability of course is systematically built up over the years.

Human relationships demand that we need to go, as far as possible, to the psychological interiors of the other person. This helps us in our relationships, in parenting and in our safety of day-to-day lives, even our daily language and interactions with others exhibit it. ... gives an example, with two different sentences: “The husband died, and then the wife died’. There is nothing particularly interesting about that sentence, but watch what happens when I add two words at the end: ‘The husband died, and then the wife died of grief.’ All of a sudden we have a view, however brief, into the psychological interior of the wife. We have an impression of her

mental state, perhaps even knowledge about her relationship with her husband” ... Our intellectual prowess, from language to mathematics to art, may have come from the powerful need to predict our neighbour’s psychological interiors” (John Medina 2008: 44-45).

II Reductionism Challenged

The hopes or the claims to comprehend consciousness very often arise from the tendency of reductionism. The consciousness and its experiences are claimed to be shown threadbare by reducing them to mere physical structures and operations. However, reductionism is severely challenged not only in bio-sciences but also in physical and chemical sciences; one can see how reductionism is shown to be much wanting in the field of consciousness as well.

1. What is Reductionism?

Reductionism argues that any complex system is the sum of its simpler individual parts (components); matter, energy and physics is all that there is and any advanced or intricate manifestation can be reduced to the basic features. It claims human beings are sophisticated automatons and all our behaviours are merely the result of the mechanical laws of our brains; the whole universe is governed by physical laws, and we as part of it, are also governed by the same laws. Our free will does not exist because we are bound by the mathematical underpinnings of reality. Consciousness, thus, is nothing but a complex manifestation of the brain and its neurons at an advanced level of its long evolution.

But some unpredictability of natural laws at the quantum level, (double slit experiment) suggest some degree of free will even for the matter and that can easily show the strong possibility of free will in human beings also. Roger Penrose tries to see the connection between consciousness and quantum physics.

2. Reductionism and Mind-Body Relationship

There are at least six exciting angles to the mind-body debate: the meaning of 'mind' and mental, the relationship between mind and body, mental causation (crucial in our day-to-day lives), intentionality, consciousness and the sense of 'self' (personhood). We are conscious of our external world and internal selves. Consciousness is built into the brain, but we don't know how exactly. It is discovered the functions of the brain to create the minimum amount of experience of consciousness. Some scientists thought consciousness is located in the claustrum (plural: claustra) is a vertical curved sheet of neurons resting beneath the cortex, connecting every other part of cortex. Others claimed, that it is created by the multiple regions of the brain working together

Brain has about 100 billion neurons, consumes about 25 % of our energy, but occupying only 2 % of our mass; brain is like the universe within; cerebral cortex in the brain is responsible for higher functions of brain like memory, perception, thought and language. If cerebellum is affected one will have difficulty in balancing, dancing or climbing, etc. but one's consciousness will not be affected. So some parts of the brain may be essential for consciousness. Brain builds models of the images and the events that come through the sensory input. The brain may not register every detail but only those details that are enough to respond to the situations; e.g. we see white light as something brightness, but actually it is a combination of 7 colours, but the brain takes it as white light in a simplified form.

Studies show that there are differences between brain processing information and our experiencing it. Brain may process information from the field of vision, but we may not be aware of it. Our experience of brain's processing is called consciousness. Some people are not aware of what is going on the brain, if it is damaged by a stroke or an accident. Either of the hemispheres can be affected and they can suffer from hemi-spatial neglect.²

It is our experiences that there is “something” that coordinates our sense-data, emotions, words, actions and reactions. What is that “something”? This is also known as ‘the binding problem’ – trying to figure out how the different parts of the brain integrate the information, coming from both external and internal senses, into conscious experience. The coordinating or binding factor is known as self, consciousness, personhood etc. cannot be reduced to the physical function of the brain. A simple example of our visual experience shows that it is near impossible to reduce to physicalism. Our two eyes see a thing and there are obviously two images on the retina of the two eyes but how come we are able to see only ONE image! As we stretch our hand and keep only the index finger straight pointing to the sky, let us close one eye to look at it with the other eye; now if we open and close the other eye vice versa, we can see the position of the finger shifting, from right to left, or vice versa, and this shows how the images on the retina different.³

Further, if reductionism were to be correct, how to explain all the biases that our unconscious minds experience? Here let us spell out some of such biases, though some of them are interconnected.

- a) Anchoring bias – we usually tend to believe the first information that comes to us; supposing a dealer says the price of the car is Rs. 30 lakhs, but he would give it for Rs. 20 lakhs, we tend to see it as a great deal! Suppose, he first says, Rs. 10 lakhs (and not Rs. 20 lakhs), we think it is not a good deal, because of the anchoring bias.
- b) Availability heuristics bias – we generally think terrorism is very dangerous, and kills many people, because we keep hearing about it in the news. But actually TV kills people 55 % more than terrorism. You are more likely to die by a cow attacking you, or coconut falling on you than being killed by a terrorist; 130 times more likely to be killed by the police, who is actually supposed to protect you from

- terrorists, than killed by terrorism itself. This is because people don't usually conclude on facts, but on the news they hear, and views of the others.
- c) Bandwagon effect – people believe in something not because they want to believe that, but because the world believes it. E.g. voting a particular candidate because of more popularity or investing in the stock market – all these, because they want to be with the majority. In the group meetings, if 9/10 people agree on something, the last person will not speak out at all.
 - d) Choice supportive bias – My choice is always the best and even if someone points out the defects of my choice, I will not heed to it. My choice of the political candidates also... my choice is the best and I will be blind to the contrary evidence.
 - e) Confirmation bias – we tend to accept what confirms our decisions or likes and ignore the opposite. It is the most committed cognitive biases; If I like sweets, and if someone says it is bad, I will try to collect the information to show the advantages of it. Even great scientists suffer from it; for instance, if an experiments gives a result contrary to what they want to prove, they tend to ignore it and look only for the confirming instances.
 - f) Ostrich bias – Looking for only positive information to support my conviction.
 - g) Outcome bias – after the decisions are made, we rarely think of the negative aspects that arose at the time of decision-making.
 - h) Overconfidence – deciding based only on our opinions; not because we have got all the right information, but in the past we have been correct; just because we got five times head when you flipped the coin, it is not certain that next time also you will get head! (Similar to the *Gambler fallacy* or *the fallacy of the maturity of chances* – it is believing that if a given event occurs more often than normal in the

past, it is likely to happen in the future as well (or vice versa).

- i) Placebo effect – if you believe that something will give you a positive result, it will happen. E.g. when a doctor gives even an ordinary vitamin tablet and if the patient believes that it will heal him/her
- j) an ordinary vitamin tablet and if you believe that it will heal you, you will be healed. (the reverse is nocebo effect).⁴
- k) Survivorship bias – it refers to judging something based on the surviving information. E.g. Reading a book on “The five things that the successful people do every day” – but there are millions those who did those things but did not succeed, but chose only a few who did succeed; another example would be, ancient buildings remain strong because they used good technology – you conclude this is based on a few buildings that stand today, but thousands have collapsed; you conclude based on only those 10 % surviving, being ignorant of 90% that have already been washed away.
- l) Selective perception – people perceive things according to the frame of reference; and ignore all that contradicts your perception.
- m) Blind spot bias – you are biased because you think you are less biased than everyone else. E.g. I give a gift to my teacher and in the next test I get a good grade; I will not say that my gift influenced her to give me a good grade, but in the case of other students and teachers, I may say ‘yes’. (it is not uncommon to hear from the students: when they get good marks, they say, “I got it”, and when they get low marks, they lament, “The professor gave me”).

3. Reductionism and Physical Laws

Reductionism is often based on some physical laws, but it is better that one is aware that the laws themselves have crucial limitations. Science is busy with inferring physical laws (natural laws).⁵ When

these laws are well-accepted they are used to explore nature further as a yardstick to understand the unknown domains of nature. In fact, that is the way, science proceeds... going from the known to the unknown. But unfortunately, *the known law itself is not always based on complete certainty*, it is often on a shaky ground... then one can imagine how ‘realistic’ or ‘objective’ or ‘true’ the new information would be! How to reduce or infer anything that is certain from those “unsettled” claims?

Physical law is objective in the sense that it is open to anyone’s testing; if the experiment is properly done the results will be the same irrespective of who is doing that experiment. However, this ‘objectivity’ does not mean that the results of the experiments represent reality as it is, whatever that might mean. Further for practical purposes we take physical laws to be certain, in reality they are only approximate. The nature of being approximate is in its very essence because we get to know nature only within the parameters or the frameworks with which we approach reality. Karl Popper explains this fact with an analogy: when we explore nature we carry our own theories and nature reveals itself accordingly; those theories are like the fishing nets and the size of the fish we can catch depends on the size of the nodes in the net; if the size of the nodes is bigger or smaller, then the size of the fish will differ accordingly. Given such approximate and objective natures of the theories, one cannot legitimately speak of the truth value of physical laws, rather one can speak of only whether they are progressive or appropriate, rather than being true or false.

Physical laws do always have the possibility of being improved upon with more sophisticated instruments and better-refined investigation. These laws can be modified, corrected or even rejected in future and therefore they are in principle corrigible and provisional. That is why, Karl Popper argues that the knowledge that we get in and through scientific enterprise does not get to the absolute truths but only near the truth (verisimilitude – nearness to the truth!). Physical laws are *schematic*, i.e. sketchy and

incomplete, as they are derived basing only on relevant factors. The choice is based on certain theories or considerations. Further, physical laws are approximate and so inexact. This inexactness is due to i) Human Imperfection; ii) Limitation of the instruments. (All mechanical and electrical instruments are limited by the Brownian Movement of their smallest parts and optical instruments can't reveal more than what is allowed by their resolving power. Further, all instruments are based on certain theories, which are themselves approximate; iii) Ignorance of the exact law: According to the Principle of Indeterminacy exact laws are unknowable in the atomic domain. iv) Vicious circle in the measurement of time duration: Time is measured by uniform motion. Uniform motion is measured by observing that equal intervals of space are traversed in equal time intervals.

Physical Laws are obtained basing upon certain assumptions. For, bare data alone can't establish a law of universal application. So a number of things are assumed, without which no generalization is possible; i) Uniformity/constancy of nature, that there is an order in nature; ii) Validity of Inductive Generalization: Scientists make use of this philosophical principle, induction, to pass from the individual physical facts in the lab to the universal fact; iii) The Principle of Fair Samples is assumed. It is impossible to examine all possible cases. Only a few specimens are taken and it is only assumed that these particular specimens truly represent the phenomenon considered, as there is no purely logical justification regarding those specimens' representation.

4. Reductionism and Realistic Science

The popular schools of Philosophy of Science of the 20th century insist upon revisiting the very understanding of the important concepts that we use in science, like observation, law, proof, explanation, field, force, evidence and so on. It is now shown that science is not just an objective, rational and progressive enterprise, rather a complex discipline embedded in a particular socio-political and cultural context.

These schools have further made it clear that not all the scientific laws, principles and concepts of the same category. Some of them need to be interpreted to make any sense. Even the seemingly simple question, ‘What is electricity?’ cannot be easily answered. One may say that “electricity is a field like gravitation. But then another question can be raise: What is a field? If we answer that a field is an oscillation, the answer begs the question: What is that oscillates? A particular difficulty arises if one goes on to quantum electrodynamics with its fields of zero-point oscillations in the vacuum. Can such a vacuum be really empty, as it should if it is truly a vacuum?” (Stanley L. Jaki 2000: 6).

We need “interpretation” of the law /theory in science. There are speculative and probability laws. For instance, in Cosmology, the Big Bang theory proposes a moment $t=0$; but it cannot be located in space and time, it is a limiting case beyond which one cannot move. This concept is left to human interpretation. Similarly, in the world of quantum physics, things are very different from those of the macro world; the particles have dual nature of being a particle and a wave at the same time; several concepts like quantum gravity, quantum tunnelling, non-locality and so on are beyond absolute definition but subjected to interpretation. Similarly, theories or proposals in many other fields, say evolutionary biology or genetic engineering, can only be interpreted, not defined or described beyond any doubt. Most of the theories about the origin of the universe or the long process of evolution can never be ‘proved’ in the usual sense of the word. As Stanley L. Jaki explains, “Science, including Einsteinian Cosmology, cannot do this [say a word about causality, or reality or unity of things] for a very simple reason: the truths of science demand experimental verification. But no scientist, no scientific instrument, can be carried beyond the universe to observe and thereby scientifically verify it. *The verification of the universe is an eminently philosophical task*” (Stanley L. Jaki 2000: 220) and this essentially involves interpretation. He further clarifies, “A physical theory can never be final for two reasons. For one, physicists can

never be sure that they will never stumble on some previously unsuspected features of matter. Also, even if they were to succeed in formulating a ‘final’ theory, they can never be sure theoretically whether it is really final” (Stanley L. Jaki 2000: 5). If science is, therefore, an enterprise of interpretation, even reductionism will not lead us to reality as it is.

It is not very difficult to realize that the ‘whole’ always seems to be more than the combination of its components; when the constituent parts come together the result of ‘wholeness’ always seems to be more than the features of the individual ingredients; for instance, a) Sodium & chlorine in themselves are poisonous, but when they come together NaCl, it is not so, and even becomes essential to make our food palatable; b) Hydrogen and oxygen are inflammable in themselves, but together as H₂O douse fire; and more interestingly, c) life is more than the coming together of all the chemicals and minerals that make life possible. One can see that the same logic can be applied to the question of consciousness too.

III Quantum Physics and Consciousness

The quantum world is really strange; objects are at more than one place at the same time, communications are taking place faster than light, the rules governing the atoms and photons seem to be alien to us. that is why Richard Feynman seems to be correct when he declares: “Anyone who claims to understand quantum theory is either lying or crazy” (Live Science, n.p.). Of course, the picture of Quantum Physics is not very disappointing, because we do understand it to a large extent; it is seen as the most successful theory today; we make computers, cameras, LEDs, lasers, power plants etc. Everything around us is made of quantum physics. Quantum physics describes objects as “wave functions”, but when we measure them, it leads to wave pattern & the measurement problem (due to the wave-particle duality). The consequences of these wave functions are quantum entanglement, quantum tunneling, Heisenberg’s Uncertainty principle and energy

quantization. Subatomic particles don't look like particles, but as wave-functions (not physical wave like water or sand waves), which are abstract mathematical descriptions. We can't predict the position of the particle with minute details, but only the location where it is highly probable to exist. It is unlike the classical physics.

But we don't know whether these wave functions are literally real or not! Wave functions are in the quantum world and when we observe they look like particles, but the change takes place in the process of measurement (known as measurement barrier); measurement collapses wave function. But we don't know how it collapses, and this is the gap in our knowledge. For instance, how to picture an electron? It seems to be a wave until we measure it, but when we measure it becomes a particle (particle-wave duality).

1. Consciousness Creating Reality?

Copenhagen interpretation of QM – often associated with Niels Bohr and Werner Heisenberg – our way of measuring determines the status of reality, so there is nothing called objective reality. It is shown by the double slit experiment – when electrons are sent through double slits it makes a wave pattern on the screen; they travel not as physical particles, or actual waves, but as probability waves. Instead of making two stripes we get a cluster of stripes on the wall, as though waves pass through. So the idea is when the electrons leave the gun, they travel as waves through the slits and overlap with each other at the other side, to produce the interference pattern; the electrons follow the probability distribution and the high probability of finding the electron is in the middle of the slit. We don't know how these *wave functions collapse*. The human consciousness is the locus where the wave function collapses. Fritjof Capra: “The human observer constitutes the final link in the chain of observational processes, and the properties of any atomic object can be understood only in terms of the object's interaction with the observer” (Fritjof Capra 1984:57).

When two overlap get mixed, it is the superposition, where the electron has the high probability to be at the amplitude, not so much at the bottom. When two waves meet, they get entangled with each other (wave entanglement); they interfere with each other and mathematically become one wave function; when we measure one, it makes correlated effect on the other, even if they are separated billions of miles away; this seems to suggest that there is a communication between them faster than light, and that make Einstein makes uncomfortable (against the theory of relativity); we can't use for any communication of information because the measurement gives random results. But the fact that they are somehow correlated there is a link stretching between that long distance, and that is known as non-locality.

According to Copenhagen interpretation, the observer has to be outside the quantum system being measured. If the observer in totality in the mathematics of quantum theory then s/he is also a part of the quantum world of probability; however we need the observer with whose interference the wave functions collapse. Therefore, "On the one hand the observer has to be 'outside' the quantum system in order to accomplish its collapse in the act of observation. On the other hand, s/he participates in the quantum process in so far as it is his/her act of observation that effects the collapse of the wave function" (Joseph Mathew 2017:210).

It is the mind that brings about irreversible change in wave function when a quantum state is measured or observed. According to Eugene Winger, "It is the entering of an impression into our consciousness which alters the wave function... consciousness enters the theory unavoidably and unalterably" (Eugene Winger 1961: 288-89). The role of observer/mind /consciousness cannot be ignored in the subatomic world, because "many physical properties of atomic particles did not even exist before the act of observation; the act of observation was necessary to bring these properties into existence" (John Barrow and Frank Tipler 1986: 460).

The idea of ‘participation of the observer’ in the quantum state can be extended, according to Wheeler, to the whole of the universe. Observers are not just spectators but participators in shaping the reality of the universe. As the wave function of the quantum object collapses in the act of measurement, so the wave function of the universe collapses in the act of measurement, so the wave function of the universe collapses only in the act of observation. John Gribbin remarks: “Taking this [collapse of the wave function] to its logical extent, Wheeler suggests that the ‘wave function’ of the entire universe (right back to the Big Bang itself) only ‘collapsed’ into reality when somebody looked at the universe and noticed its existence” (John Barrow and Frank Tipler 1986: 22).

2. Atomic and Cellular Actions in Our Body – Conscious?

Reductionism seems to be humanly impossible for many reasons. For instance, given the vast numbers of atoms in our human body or the unimaginably vast number of galaxies and stars in the space really fill us with awe and wonder. More the discoveries that the world of science come across the more we are filled with a sense of mystery over the mastery of creation; the complexity and intricacy embedded in nature really baffle us. Our human body in an average has about one hundred trillion cells and each cell is found to have about 200 trillion molecules; they all perform thousands of functions in a particular order and timings. *All these chemical actions and reactions seem to be purposeful and conscious, and which theory can explain the consciousness at the molecular levels?* Further, each cell has a nucleus, which contains DNA, where one finds thirty thousand genes; in every gene there about 1000 nucleotides and each one of them is having 50 atoms. Then one can imagine the number of atoms in our body (it is about 10^{18} atoms!). In our brain there are about 100 billion neuron cells and each neuron can have 10000 connections. All these incredibly complex and mind-boggling structures stagger us obviously. This can easily take us from physics to metaphysics, from materiality to spirituality. That is why, Francis Collins rightly wonders: “I

experience a sense of awe at the realization that humanity now knows something only God knew before. It is a deeply moving sensation that helps me appreciate the spiritual side of life".⁶

Conclusion

Having gone through all these reflections one can easily realize that the complete construal of consciousness does not seem to be possible. Nevertheless, human beings need not fester about it. For, our brain has evolved only to survive in a variety of hostile conditions, brought out by the forces of nature and other animals; it has not evolved to comprehend the whole universe, nor to fathom its own functions completely; it is designed to: a) solve problems, b) issues of survival, c) in an unstable outdoor environment, and d) to do so in nearly constant motion" – with these abilities we are able to conquer the world to a large extent, though we are very weak in many ways compared to other species on the earth. Since we are not stronger, we used our brains to become smarter. We are so weak and helpless that other ferocious animals, natural forces or even air bubble in our blood stream⁷, or a small piece of a bone stuck at the wind pipe of our throat can kill us instantaneously.

Somehow we tend to give undue importance to rational aspects of our existence, which makes us uncomfortable with our ignorance about anything. Of course, rational beings as we are, our curiosity is very essential for the growth of knowledge but the same rationality must teach us that it is alright to be ignorant in some matters, and not to be irritated or disturbed by our ignorance. We need to take all legitimate efforts to remove ignorance, but when we are pushed to the edges, we need to learn to live with the shadows of ignorance.

Ignorance is not always bad; it is not always a curse either. There are real advantages of ignorance, not just of an individual but as human race. Some of the advantages are: Ignorance makes us *humble to know more* (even the scientists know, not only what they know, but also they know that they can't know how much they

don't know!); ignorance encourages us to be *open to learn from others and nature* (and even to learn how to learn!), and to correct our own mistakes; it teaches us that knowledge enterprise is a communitarian task; it enables us to appreciate and respect plurality, and allows dissenting voices; it makes the realistic picture of science in particular, and of the whole humanity in general, possible; it helps us to grow in our relationships, knowledge, spirituality and personality and finally it makes the very knowledge process possible.

If we focus unduly on having knowledge about everything and anything, and if we insist upon total predictability in every domain, we have some disadvantages as well. We, as individuals and as human race, can become frustrated over our inability to know everything. We lose spontaneity and become over-conscious and too calculative in our approaches. We tend to consider ourselves omniscient and omnipotent, to take the destiny of humanity and that of nature into our hands; it is not uncommon today to see people how they get extremely disturbed and disoriented while facing even small failures or disappointments in life. Total predictability will remove spontaneity and curiosity, and that in turn will make life boring and prosaic. Knowing everything in advance is not possible in our human relationships and it will have serious repercussions as well. Breaking the rules of conventions sometimes results in breakthroughs. Our daring nature to be different would be damaged if we always insist upon treading the known paths in safety. If everyone knows everything there is no need of any one in the world. Social beings as we are grow by give-and-take relationships.⁸

Thus, it seems to be very logical to conclude that we can never understand the nature and the functions of the brain completely, because we need to use a similar brain in our head to map the functions of another brain; and that in turn seems to teach us in unambiguous terms that we can never completely understand consciousness either, as it is related to brain. Yes, as long as we

take ‘conscious’ efforts to study the intricacies of consciousness we can never master in our understanding what that consciousness means or implies! Nevertheless, that fact, needless to say, need not deter humanity from exploring into the intricacies of consciousness, which can help us in identifying the purpose and meaning of our lives.

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Jayard: A Complete Construal of Consciousness

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¹ There are several tests to check the intensity, ability and quality of our awareness; one can check these sites: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FWSxSQsspiQ> and <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1nL5ulsWMYc>.

² Hemispatial neglect is a neuropsychological condition, caused by strokes and brain unilateral injury to the right cerebral hemisphere, leading up to 80% of visual neglect of the left-hand side of space; such persons cannot perceive and process the stimuli on one side of the body or environment, due to the lack of sensations; they even ignore or disown their own left limbs—in the left side of space. so they with right-sided brain damage often fail to be aware of objects to their left, demonstrating neglect of leftward items, even large things and people; they tend often to eat from eat from only one side of a plate, write on one side of a page, shave or make-up only the non-neglected side. Right-sided spatial neglect is found to be rare because there is redundant processing of the right space by both the left and right cerebral hemispheres, whereas in most left-dominant brains the left space is only processed by the right cerebral hemisphere. See: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hemispatial_neglect.

³ This concept is related to the *parallax vision* - the apparent displacement or the difference in apparent direction of an object as seen from two different points not on a straight line with the object especially: the

angular difference in direction of a celestial body as measured from two points on the earth's orbit. The term “parallax” refers to the apparent movement of objects when viewed from different positions. The everyday example of this is seen driving on the highway-- when you look out the window, electrical poles near the road seem to zoom past, while trees in the distance appear to slowly drift by.

⁴ I have elsewhere elaborated on the placebo effect, and its opposite nocebo effect; see: *Is Body Merely Bodily? – Reflections on Human Body as a Symbol in Bio- and Medical Sciences in Philosophizing the Body – Physical, Social, Psychological and Spiritual Dimensions*, ed. by Nishant A. Irudayadason (New Delhi: Christian World Imprints and Association of Christian Philosophers of India, 2016, pp. 151-160.

⁵ There are different types of laws available in the domain of science; for instance, one comes across theoretical laws, experimental laws, qualitative laws, quantitative laws, deterministic laws, statistical (probabilistic) laws. But for our purpose here we just focus on physical laws in general.

⁶ The renowned geneticist Francis S. Collins explains through personal testimony how and why faith and reason can and do coexist peacefully; he is convinced that both are in fact complementary. For more details, see his work, *The Language of God: A Scientist Presents Evidence for Belief* (New York: Free Press, 2007).

⁷ An embolism is a blocked artery caused by a foreign body, such as a blood clot or an air bubble. The body's tissues and organs need oxygen, which is transported around the body in the bloodstream. Most embolisms happen to people who have risk factors for blood clot formation, such as smoking and heart disease. Other risk factors for other types of emboli include high blood pressure, atherosclerosis (buildup of fatty plaque in the blood vessels), high cholesterol, and obesity.

⁸ For more details, see my paper: Stephen Jayard, “Can Ignorance Be Ignored?” in *Science-Religion Dialogue and Its Contemporary Significance – Interdisciplinary Essays in Honour of Prof. Dr Kuruvilla Pandikattu*, ed. by Binoy Pichalakattu (Bengaluru: ATC Publishers), 2018), 258-262.